

Table 2: The RIA-calculated Properties. While detailed descriptions of the binding property RIA outputs are available from Rosetta, brief descriptions are provided here to facilitate understanding of the PEPBI RIA binding property data.

RIA Property Name	Brief Description
total_score	Total energy for the complex
complex_normalized	Total energy for the complex divided by the total number of amino acids
dG_cross	Predicted binding energy using cross interface terms (not recommended for use)
dG_cross/dSASAx100	dG_cross divided by change in buried surface area
dG_separated	Predicted binding energy
dG_separated/dSASAx100	dG_separated divided by change in buried surface area.
dSASA_hphobic	Change in hydrophobic solvent accessible surface area.
dSASA_int	Change in total solvent accessible surface area
dSASA_polar	Change in polar solvent accessible surface area
delta_unsatHbonds	Change in the number of unsatisfied hydrogen bonds upon complex formation
dslf_fa13	Energy from disulfide bond geometries
fa_atr	Attractive force between atoms from the Lennard-Jones potential
fa_dun	Internal energy of side chains based on statistics from Dunbrack
fa_elec	Columbic electrostatic force between atoms
fa_intra_rep	Repulsive force between atoms in the same residue in Lennard-Jones potential
fa_intra_sol_xover4	Lazaridis-Karplus implicit solvation energy within a residue
fa_rep	Repulsive force between atom from the Lennard- Jones potential
fa_sol	Lazaridis-Karplus implicit solvation energy
hbond_E_fraction	Fraction of dG_separated from interprotein hydrogen bonds
hbond_bb_sc	Hydrogen bond energy between backbones and side chains
hbond_lr_bb	Hydrogen bond energy between backbones of distant residues in primary sequence
hbond_sc	Hydrogen bond energy between side chains
hbond_sr_bb	Hydrogen bond energy between backbones of nearby residues in primary sequence
hbonds_int	Number of interprotein hydrogen bonds in the interface
lk_ball_wtd	Asymmetric Lazaridis-Karplus implicit solvation energy
nres_all	Total number of amino acids in the complex
nres_int	Total number of amino acids in the interface
omega	Energy from omega dihedral angles
p_aa_pp	Probability of amino acid side chain conformations
packstat	Rosetta's packing statistic score for the interface where 0=bad and 1=perfect
per_residue_energy_int	Average energy of interface residues
pro_close	Energy of proline ring closures
rama_prepro	Ramachandran preferences
ref	Reference energies for each amino acid
sc_value	How well the peptide and protein fit together
side1_normalized	The side1_score divided by the number of protein interface residues
side1_score	In PEPBI, the energy of the protein
side2_normalized	The side2_score divided by the number of peptide interface residues
side2_score	In PEPBI, the energy of the peptide
yhhplanarity	A special potential to keep TYR hydroxyls in the aromatic plane